
The Impact of Inspirational Motivation on Organizational Sustainability of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Bayelsa State.

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Abstract

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are faced with numerous challenges such as economic instability, technological changes, resource constraints, and heightened competition. Extensive review of literature that discussed the significance of leadership paradigms in enhancing organizational resilience, revealed a notable gap regarding the impact of inspirational motivation on innovativeness of SMEs in Bayelsa state. This study examines the impact of inspirational motivation on the organizational sustainability of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Bayelsa State. The research explores how visionary and inspirational leadership motivation can foster strategic resource mobilization, innovation, and adaptive capacities essential for long-term survival. Data was collected from 84 directors and managers of 42 SMEs in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state. Data collected were analyzed using Spearman Rank Order Correlation Co-efficient. The findings revealed a positive and significant relationship between inspirational motivation and sustainability of SMEs. The study concludes that fostering inspirational motivation within small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Yenagoa can lead to a positive impact on the organization's sustainability. The study therefore recommend that small and medium-sized enterprises owners and managers should undergo leadership training programs that focus on motivational techniques as this could equip them with the skills to inspire their teams and foster a positive and empowering work environment.

Keywords: Inspirational motivation, organizational sustainability, resourcefulness, innovativeness, adaptiveness.

1.0 Introduction

In today's global business environment, firms are faced with diverse challenges like political instability, economic crises, new technologies and heightened competition. As such, business entities need to strategies and adopt efficient means of deploying resources and gain competitive advantage (Hover et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2013; Boylan & Turner, 2017). Ajagbe et al. (2015) noted that the continued depressed state of the economy has huge negative implications on the health and survival of firms. It has resulted in market instability making it increasingly difficult for the predictive ability of firm managers. Many firms in developing economies are daily confronted with a harsh operational environment which impinges on their capacity to function at the desired level. These challenges account for poor service delivery to all stakeholders and in some cases the increased rate of employee turnover (Kodama, 2019). There is an observed increase in the number of failed firms and this according to Walumbwa and Lawler (2013) is owed to inability to craft long-term plans required to mitigate the turbulence associated with the business environment, their survival and sustainability.

The increase in energy costs required for operation has increased the burden of managing firm sustainability. As crucial as the concept of corporate sustainability is, its discourse has been largely left in the domain of large firms which by implication has shifted attention on small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) to the sidelines. This scenario does not mean well for their survival and sustainability when viewed against environmental turbulence. Rubaca and Majid-Khan (2021) observed that owing to SMEs financial and operational resource constraints, the development of their competencies and capacities that support sustainability has become a concern. Organizational sustainability is a firm ability to mobilize resources and take necessary actions that undermine the swift changing nature of the business environment today while at the same time providing the means for the future of the firms. This entails getting committed to strategic actions for seeing their markets, sustaining their markets with new products, and innovative operational processes amongst others for competitiveness. Chang (2010) argued that SMEs have the huge responsibility of driving economic growth and industrialization therefore are required to be critical about the complexities and dynamics of the environment to spur actions that engender sustainability and long-term survival. Sustainability orientations of firms entail generating, acquiring and mobilizing, strategic resources, swift response to changing market demands through improved rate of innovativeness, seeking new opportunities and exploiting same and adapting to the changes. Achieving the battery of strategic actions that characterize sustainability is a major task particularly amongst SMEs with obvious huge resource constraints. It involves a set of well-coordinated short-term plans that are quite engaging at all levels of organizations. Securing existing markets and exploiting new ones call for ardent innovative practices which have remained unfamiliar with SMEs especially in developing economies with low technological profile (Doran & Ryan, 2017). If the thesis of properly coordinated plans and actions is anything to buy, El-Hai (2019) believed that deploying inspirational approaches to managing SMEs operators is likely to trigger initiation and effective management of all such short and long-term plans for corporate sustainability. In other words, engaging inspirational motivation managers clearly direct the workforce goals. Carvalho (2018) noted that only proactive and innovative businesses could deal with this competitive digitalization. The organizations are still required to identify new innovative approaches to deal with emerging technologies. Contemporary leadership discourse has brought to the fore multiple leadership approaches in which visionary and transformational approaches for leading have gained prominence. Leadership paradigms are shifting from traditional to visionary also termed charismatic, transformational or inspirational leadership.

Asif et al. (2019) argued that transformational leaders uplift the contribution of team members to accept the mission and purpose of the organization by motivating them to sacrifice their interest and achieve the common interest of the group. Moreover, visionary leadership transforms individual desires, doctrines, preferences and ambitions into shared and common interest by sharing values, vision, collective decision making and authorization (Zhou et al., 2018). Furthermore, followers of transformational leaders are empowered and work independently for a collective purpose. They are inspired by the charisma and vision of their leaders (Jing et al., 2020). Such features as demonstrated according to Gerald (2017) are likely to provide the means to corporate sustainability.

Wang et al. (2016) observed that intellectually engaging moments instigates innovativeness through shared knowledge. The goal in this circumstance is to ensure quality service delivery as a recipe for sustainability. Organizational sustainability studies have sought to explore factors that stimulate and enhance corporate sustainability. Nkurunziza et al. (2019) had linked dynamic capabilities with organizational sustainability. Teece et al. (2009) have equally linked with organizational innovativeness which is of a component of sustainability. These studies notwithstanding, it is yet unclear the impact of inspirational motivation on organizational sustainability which clearly shows a gap in knowledge. Despite several studies on inspirational motivation and organizational outcomes not much attention has been focused on this relationship amongst small and medium scale firms. Therefore, this study seeks to establish the relationship between inspirational motivation and organizational sustainability in small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

Small and medium sized firms are undoubtedly experiencing multiple challenges resulting from the complex character of their organizational environment. Their capacity to function optimally has been consistently diminished owing to the depressed nature of the economy, the emergence of new technologies, globalization that have opened markets with attendant increase in competition and depleting resources which affects their working capital. Large firms commonly dominate their market environment as they are leveraged with huge operational capital and perhaps more reliable production processes that undermine SMEs capacity to readily serve their market and ensure quality service delivery.

Arising from low capital amidst other operational resources, small and medium sized firms hardly show capacity in getting involved in research effort with a view to innovatively engage their markets. In other words, poor innovative behavior has characterized their functioning; making it difficult for their sustained survival. Udoko (2021) observed that small firms particularly in developing economies do not promptly provide new products or improve existing ones in the wake of the expanding markets due to their inability to acquire and mobilize resources for creativeness needed to attract patronage. Again, considering the dynamic nature of the environment that is notably volatile, small and medium scale firms' adaptive ability is associated vulnerabilities is fundamental to their survival. Akibe (2021) noted that up to 52% of small and medium sized firms have gone distressed due to their poor resilience behaviour that makes it difficult for adaptiveness to changes in their business environment.

Considering the degree of SMEs morbidity especially in developing economies, where they are expected to contribute to economic development, Palmer and Bui (2019) argues that continuous search for all such factors that strengthens their competitive ability and ensure their sustainability must be underscored. Kappa and James (2019) had investigated cultural orientation and SMEs sustainability in Kumasi province, and a positive relationship was found. Gilbert et al (2017) examined the correlation between owner's personality traits and

SMEs survival in South-West Nigeria. The result also showed significant correlation. These notwithstanding, the place of leadership on corporate survival have been noted in extant works (Miller et al, 2017; Alero, 2017; Emerana, 2014). These studies examined leadership styles in large firms and public owned institutions. For instance, Alero (2017) investigated transformational leadership and sustainability of tertiary institutions in Kwara State. The result though showed positive relationship, the work practice policies and values are not same with the SMEs as private business entities, therefore may not serve their purpose. These represent therefore a knowledge gap that needs further research. Against this backdrop, this study is aimed at investigating the impact of inspirational leadership on organisational sustainability of SMEs in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

Research Questions

The study seeks to provide answers to the following research questions:

- i. What is the relationship between inspirational motivation and resourcefulness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa?
- ii. What is the relationship between inspirational motivation and innovativeness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa?
- iii. What is the relationship between inspirational motivation and adaptiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa?

Research Hypotheses

The following null research hypotheses were formulated and tested:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between inspirational motivation and resourcefulness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between inspirational motivation and innovativeness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between inspirational motivation and adaptiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa.

2.0 Literature Review

Inspirational Motivation

According to Hornby (2003), inspiration is the process of being cognitively aroused to act or feel, particularly to act in a creative manner. It is that notion or concept that an artist has in mind but keeps hidden in their subconscious because they haven't yet succeeded in visualizing it in the outside world. Thrash and Elliot (2004) described inspiration as a mood of motivation that encourages people to carry out their ideas. According to his opinion, inspiration is an internal motivation with a strong cognitive component (Böttger et al., 2017). When fresh concepts and ideas are communicated, leaders are inspired (Thrash & Elliot, 2004). Hinsch et al. (2020) claimed that inspiration is difficult to achieve without at least some degree of realism. Therefore, by imagining a new reality, leaders should provide employees a realistic experience. Buheji and Thomas (2016) posit inspiration as a currency and that it comes in a variety of forms and degrees. These various inspiration modes entail the capacity of an individual, an organization, a community, or even the government to inspire others. The ability to produce or exchange the currency of inspiration, as well as other crucial currencies associated with it, such as the currency of invention or creativity, the currency of knowledge, or the currency of learning, can affect an organization's ability to respond to development requirements and problems. Employees that work for inspirational leaders are motivated to push themselves beyond their comfort zones and engage in their tasks above the basic requirements (Avolio & Bass, 1995). Sosik et al. (1998) argued that leaders have an inspirational role when they encourage their followers to accept problems and

see them as opportunities. When a leader conveys his task and ideas to his team members and inspires them to believe in the power of working together to achieve the goals, he or she demonstrates leadership inspiration. They therefore guarantee the best outcomes. Such leaders put a strong emphasis on their teams' dedication to achieving longer-term objectives and use creativity in their task-solving. Leaders who are inspired will be able to inspire their followers and employees to be enthusiastic about and committed to the goals and objectives of the company.

According to Popa (2012), a leader's capacity for inspiration allows him to convert and communicate a vision with complete zeal and assurance. Den Hartog et al. (2002), described inspiration as acting in a way that people would want to follow, where there is two-way communication and where relationships and efforts are valued. In order for their team members to fulfill the organization's beliefs and goals, these leaders create a demanding environment, maintain team motivation, and instill optimism in them (Bass et al., 2003). He holds that a leader's inspiration and other motivating aspects of the workplace culture have a significant impact on how devoted a worker is to his or her goals and to their organization (Mahendru & Sharma, 2006).

Inspirational leaders build attainable strategies for accomplishing their objectives and then mobilize support for those plans by explaining them to their people in a convincing and understandable way (Walumbwa & Lawler, 2013). This is thought to inspire workers to collaborate in order to achieve a common objective and meet or exceed predetermined goals, or what is commonly known as extra role performance (Uzonna, 2013). By focusing on a greater cause and raising followers' intrinsic desire, dedication, and effort, which results in performance improvement, inspiration is concerned with motivating employees to a higher level of contribution and productivity (Minja & Barine, 2014). According to Bass; and Riggio (2006), inspirational leaders are able to instill a strong sense of teamwork among their followers, motivating them to achieve the stated organizational goals. Through motivation, supportive leaders share the value-based ambitions of the organization's members, enhancing value congruence between the company and its employees (Brown & Treviño, 2009). This helps followers to be more closely identified with the goals and objectives of the organization and to match their performance with that of the organization. In addition to using inspiring motivation, leaders can inspire their teams to work harder and produce more (Barrick et al., 2015). By inspiring others, the leaders encourage junior-level staff to express their thoughts and perspectives, increasing the number of exchanges within the company (Datche & Mukulu, 2015).

The Concept of Organisational Sustainability

Organizational sustainability is receiving more attention from academics and practitioners alike. The concept of sustainability is most frequently linked to endurance, upholding fundamental ideals or goals, and taking care of other people's needs (Bateh et al., 2013). Sustainability is defined as "development that satisfies current needs while maintaining the ability of future generations to satisfy their own needs" (Cross et al., 2017). Securing a higher quality of life for everyone through responsible economic success, equitable social advancement, and effective ecological conservation is the overarching goal of sustainable development (Cavagnaro & Curiel., 2012), along with striking the appropriate balance between them. Without organizations and individuals, sustainable development cannot be accomplished. Therefore, according to human resource management experts, SME's need to intensify their attention on a sustainable approach to deal with people who are increasingly vulnerable to environmental disasters, rising economic disparity, and employees who are increasingly anxious, burned out, or insecure about their jobs. Through the prevention and

elimination of harassment, exploitation, and abuse of any person, human resource practices should respect human rights.

Resourcefulness

The term resourcefulness describes the capacity to handle challenging circumstances or uncommon difficulties by making effective or creative use of the resources at hand. Resourcefulness is the ability to recognize and seize chances early in economic endeavors (Kanungo & Misra, 1992; Misra & Kumar, 2000). One who is resourceful can overcome resource limitations and take advantage of institutional inefficiencies to their financial advantage. Young businesses can benefit greatly from resourcefulness, which is a proactive attitude motivated by resource constraints that looks at challenges in order to find solution (Baker & Nelson, 2005). Through imaginative thinking, inspiration, and the utilization of local resources, resourcefulness has the ability to promote strategic capacity among disadvantaged populations (Ganz, 2005). Particularly in the service sector, resourceful leaders deliver the greatest services because of their inventiveness (Harris et al., 2013). Even in situations with little resources, they face obstacles and succeed in doing so (Rubaca & Majid Khan, 2021). They are prepared to handle challenges and barriers, such as changing work conditions, low resource environments, more workload, etc. because they have the resources needed to complete the job (Haynie et al., 2020).

Innovativeness

Innovativeness is crucial to an organization's success, especially when employees go above and beyond to find the greatest solution to meet customers' expectations. Acar and Özşahin (2018) opine that the finest resources for helping businesses stay competitive in the rapidly changing business environment are innovation. The modern consumer is looking for distinctive goods that may be tailored to their own requirements as well as sales strategies that establish enduring relationships. It follows that innovation forms the foundation of intrapreneurship because adopting new and creative techniques is a prevalent trait among performing personnel (Ajagbe et al., 2015). Bedi (2019) stated that, in contrast to non-innovative organizations, innovation increases a company's ability to compete, generally enhances its internal capacities, and increases its ability to respond to changing circumstances and market demand.

Innovativeness is the mean and process through which innovation is achieved and known as a determinant of performance (Bodlaj & Čater, 2019). del Mar Fuentes-Fuentes et al. (2017) argued that innovativeness is the degree to which an individual or other unit of adoption is comparatively sooner in adopting new ideas than any other component of the system and as such innovativeness signifies behavioural change. The ability of a company to continue innovatively in a sustainable way determines its long-term success. However, there is a lack of information in the literature regarding what constitutes innovation capabilities in organizations and how to build and sustain them.

Adaptiveness

Adaptability is also a term that has emerged from several disciplines. Amah and Baridam (2012) included the idea of adaptability to their analysis of the vulnerability of Mexican agricultural systems. The authors contend that adaptability is a key characteristic of vulnerability and may be defined as the extent to which a system can modify its circumstances to move to a less vulnerable condition. Additionally, the idea of adaptability lies at the heart of current business continuity methods. Adaptability is defined by Boylan and Turner (2017) as an organization's capacity to change its strategy, operations, management

systems, governance structure, and decision-support capabilities in order to resist shocks and disturbances. The ability of a system to adapt to changes in its surroundings and to recover from harm to internal system components that impair the system's ability to function are both examples of adaptability. The way a system responds to change can be more mechanistically or organically, depending on the system's ability for self-organization. These two spectrums can be seen in both individuals and in organizations. One such instance is the tendency for some organizations' crisis management structures to be more mechanistic command-and-control structures, in which the system's response is guided and coordinated by formalized communication channels. Other organizations, in comparison, are more organic, displaying diffuse communication (using informal relationships as efficient communication conduits), decentralized decision-making, and influence and power based on expert knowledge rather than on official authority (Burrell, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory

Rogers postulated the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory in 1962 and was one of the earliest theories in social sciences. It first appeared in communication to describe how an idea or product gathers steam and diffuses (or spreads) within a particular population or social system over time. According to Rogers, diffusion of innovation is the process by which an innovation is communicated over time among the members of a social system through specific channels. Any idea, practice, or object that is perceived as new by an individual or other unit of adoption is considered to be an innovation in the eyes of its adopter (Miller, 2015). People eventually adopt a new idea, behaviour, or product as a part of a social system because of this dissemination. Adoption is the act of changing one's behaviour from what it was previously (e.g., using a new sense, learning a new behaviour, etc.). The person must believe the concept, conduct, or product to be novel or unique for it to be adopted. This makes it possible for diffusion (Šmitienė et al., 2021).

In a social system, the adoption of a novel concept, activity, or item otherwise seen as innovation does not occur simultaneously; rather, it is a process in which certain individuals are more likely to accept the innovation than others. Essentially, those who adopt innovations sooner than those who acquire them later have different traits. Understanding the traits of the target demographic that will facilitate or impede acceptance of the invention is crucial when promoting it to that group. Although the bulk of the general population tends to fall towards the middle of the five recognized adopter categories, it is still important to comprehend the traits of the target market. Diverse tactics are employed while advertising an innovation to appeal to the various adopter segments (Chang, 2010).

3.0 Methodology

The population of this study consists of all small and medium-sized firms listed in the SMEDAN Schedule (2022) Bayelsa State. The list has 137 registered SMEs. This study considered SMEs that have operated for not less than seven (7) years and not less than fifteen (15) man workforces. Based on these parameters, 42 SMEs constitute the primary population of the study. The Directors and a manager from each of the SMEs were the participants, thus, making the actual population to be 84. Since the population can be feasibly covered the entire population was covered for the study.

Data analysis was done descriptively and inferentially. The descriptive analysis was used for the demographic and univariate analysis and this involved mean scores, frequencies, percentages and standard deviation. In the case of the inferential, the Spearman Rank Order Correlation Co-efficient statistic was used.

Inspirational Motivation and Measures of Organizational Sustainability

Table 1 shows the result of correlation matrix obtained for inspirational motivation and measures of organizational sustainability. The table revealed the statistical test of significance (p - value), which enables us to answer our research questions and generalize our findings to the study population.

Table 1: Correlations for Inspirational Motivation and Measures of Organizational Sustainability

		Inspirational Motivation	Resourcefulness	Innovativeness	Adaptiveness	
Spearman's rho	Inspirational Motivation	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.433**	.777**	.948**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000
		N	80	80	80	80
	Resourcefulness	Correlation Coefficient	.433**	1.000	.322**	.385**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.004	.000
		N	80	80	80	80
	Innovativeness	Correlation Coefficient	.777**	.322**	1.000	.700**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.004	.	.000
		N	80	80	80	80
	Adaptiveness	Correlation Coefficient	.948**	.385**	.700**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.
		N	80	80	80	80

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Survey Data 2023

Table 1 shows a Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient (rho) of 0.433 on the relationship between inspirational motivation and resourcefulness. This value implies that a moderate positive relationship exists between the variables. The direction of the relationship indicates that the correlation is positive; implying that an increase in resourcefulness was because of the adoption of inspirational motivation. Therefore, there is a moderate positive correlation between inspirational motivation and resourcefulness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between inspirational motivation and resourcefulness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

From the result shown in table 1, the sig- calculated is less than significant level (p = 0.000 < 0.05). Hence, based on this finding the null hypothesis (H₀₁) earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between inspirational motivation and resourcefulness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

Similarly, Table 1 shows a (rho) of 0.777 on the relationship between inspirational motivation and innovativeness and the value depicts a strong relationship between the variables. Also, the direction of the relationship indicates that the correlation is positive; and means that an increase in innovativeness was because of the adoption of inspirational motivation. As a result, there is a very strong positive correlation between inspirational motivation and innovativeness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between inspirational motivation and innovativeness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa.

The result obtained from table 1 shows that the sig-calculated is less than significant level ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis (H₀₂) earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between inspirational motivation and innovativeness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

Furthermore, the (rho) value of 0.948 on the relationship between inspirational motivation and adaptiveness. This value implies a very strong relationship between the variables, while the direction of the relationship is positive implying that an increase in adaptiveness was because of the adoption of inspirational motivation. Therefore, there is a very strong positive correlation between inspirational motivation and adaptiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between inspirational motivation and adaptiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

Also, the result obtained from table 1 indicates that sig-calculated is less than significant level ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis (H₀₃) earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between inspirational motivation and adaptiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

Therefore, the results for H₀₁, H₀₂ and H₀₃ with regards to the relationship between inspirational motivation and measures of organizational sustainability are stated as follows:

- i. There is a moderate positive significant relationship between inspirational motivation and resourcefulness of small and medium sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.
- ii. There is a strong positive significant relationship between inspirational motivation and innovativeness of small and medium-sized enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.
- iii. There is a very strong positive significant relationship between inspirational motivation and adaptiveness of small and medium-sized firms in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state.

Discussion of Findings

The findings showed that there is a strong positive significant relationship between inspirational motivation and organisational sustainability amongst SMEs in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state. This finding corroborates with the earlier works of Hasija et al. (2019) that examined the relationship between inspirational motivation and employee engagement in business schools in Durban and found a positive relationship between inspirational motivation and employee engagement. Also, the finding conforms with the findings of Manshor et al. (2020) who examined the linkages between inspirational motivation and organizational commitment and found a significant relationship and further indicated that much of the exhibition of employee commitment is predicted up to 47% by inspirational motivation. Likewise, it supports the study carried out by Rahman et al. (2023) on the influence of inspirational motivation on employee pro-social behaviour among public work department employees in Slovenia. The study findings revealed a strong positive relationship between the variables, and the relationship was emphasized with co-worker support component of pro-social behavior. Similarly, the current finding agrees with Krishman (2022) who conducted a study on inspirational motivation and organizational competitiveness in the furniture making sector in Turkey and found that there is a significant relationship between inspirational motivation as a predictor of organizational competitiveness, therefore emphasized clear communication of work goals to all work members for effective and efficient task handling.

Furthermore, this study findings align with that of Tvedt et al (2022) that investigated the nature of relationship between inspirational motivation and corporate innovativeness of food and beverage firms in Holland. The study revealed that 53% of the behavior of innovativeness in the firms is predicted by the inspirational motivation approach of the managers. The study concludes that inspirational motivation correlates with corporate innovativeness of the food and beverage sectors. Hasidja et al. (2019) examined the impact of inspirational motivation as a component of transformational leadership and corporate performance of 4-Star hotels in Istanbul and concluded that inspirational motivation impacts on performance of four-Star hotels in Istanbul. Furthermore, the findings of the study conducted by Gbasabeh et al. (2015) revealed a positive significant relationship between inspirational motivation and corporate health of the banking sector in Malawi.

4.0 Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concludes that inspirational motivation positively improves organisational sustainability amongst SMEs in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state. This denotes that fostering inspirational motivation within Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Yenagoa can lead to a positive impact on the organization's sustainability. Inspirational motivation involves articulating a compelling vision, providing a sense of purpose, and encouraging employees to work towards common goals with enthusiasm and passion.

5.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the conclusion and implications of the study, the following recommendations were put forward:

- i. Small and medium-sized enterprises owners and managers can undergo leadership training programs that focus on motivational techniques. These programs can equip them with the skills to inspire their teams and foster a positive and empowering work environment.
- ii. Owners and managers of small and medium-sized enterprises should implement open communication channels within the organization that can enhance inspirational motivation. Also, conduct regular team meetings, encourage open communication, and opportunities for employee feedback which can contribute to a culture of motivation and resourcefulness.
- iii. Owners and managers of small and medium-sized enterprises should undergo training and development programs that focus on fostering inspirational motivation. This can involve learning how to articulate a compelling vision, providing purposeful direction, and enhancing communication skills.

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